

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS "MADNESS" IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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ABSTRACT

Phraseological turnover conveys the figurative meaning of the entire turnover as a whole, resulting from the original meanings of words in various free combinations. In this article, phraseological units with the meaning "Madness" are considered from the point of view of a broad approach, that is, they include all groups of language units, as well as stable predicative phrases that have a figurative and expressive meaning.

INTRODUCTION: Uzbek and English phraseological units with the meaning "Madness" represent a significant group of phraseological units with specific features. Among them, there are phraseological units of all types (according to the classification of V.V. Vinogradov): phraseological fusions, unity and combinations. Most of the stable units found by us are primordial in origin (that is, they arose and function in a given language) and reflect the facts of history, traditions, customs and beliefs of their people. Some phraseological units found were borrowed from other languages; there are also phraseological units of literary origin.

ANALYSES OF LITERATURES AND METHODS: The coincidence of the plan of expression and the plan of the content of

phraseological units of the compared languages leads to the emergence of a series of structural-semantic equivalents. Since the match can be complete or incomplete, we can single out complete structural-semantic equivalents and incomplete structural-semantic equivalents.

DISCUSSION and RESULTS: The full structural-semantic phraseological equivalents of Uzbek and English are phraseological units, which have complete semantic identity and complete identity of the component composition [Arsenteva, 1989: 97-98]. We attributed the following phraseological units to them with the meaning "Madness":

1. go out of (or lose) one's mind

lose = lose, mind = mind;

2. lose one's grip (of / on) (literal translation "to lose power over someone") - to lose power over oneself

lose = lose, grip = power;

3. like a red rag to a bull

acts like a bull red color (rag)

like = like, to a bull = on a bull, red = red, rag = rag;

4. rip and tear (lit. per. "tear and throw") - tear and throw

rip = tear, and = and, tear = throw;

5. go up the wall (lit. per. "climb the wall") - climb the wall

go up = climb on, the wall = wall.

As we can see, these pairs of phraseological units have the absolute identity of semantics and structure. Despite the fact that from a syntactic point of view they are not absolute equivalents, their lexical composition is identical to each other.

Incomplete structural-semantic phraseological equivalents are phraseological units, in which, with complete semantic identity, there are some differences in the component composition (within the studied group of stable units) [Arsenteva, 1989: 100].

This group includes the following pairs of phraseological units:

1. be side oneself with smth. (literal translation "to be near oneself from something") - to be beside oneself

identical components: be = to be, oneself = oneself; non-identical components: beside("near"), with smth.("from smth."), outside;

2. have a screw loose (or missing) (literal translation "loose screw / lost screw") - there are not enough screws (screws) (in the head) identical components: a screw = screw; non-identical components: loose ("free"), have ("to have"), not enough;

3. go off one's head (lit. per. "leave your head") - to lose your head identical components: head = head; non-identical components: go off ("leave"), lose;

4. be out (or take leave) of one's senses (literal translation "to be out of mind") - to lose your mind identical components: senses = mind; non-identical components: be out ("be out"), lose;

5. get (or have) one's (or smb's) blood up

identical components: blood= blood; non-identical components: get up ("wake up"), smb's ("someone"), boils, in the veins;

6. go over the edge (lit. per. "to go to the extreme") - to bring identical components to the extreme: the edge - extreme; non-identical components: go over ("go over"), bring;

7. make smb.'s blood boil

- blood boils in the veins

identical components: boil = boil, blood = blood; non-identical components: make smb.'s ("awaken in someone"), in the veins;

8. hit the ceiling (lit. per. "beat on the ceiling") - to beat against the wall identical components: hit = beat; non-identical components: the ceiling ("ceiling"), against the wall;

9. hot under the collar

identical components: hot = hot; non-identical components: under ("under") the collar ("collar"), on the hand. Despite the difference in the nominal components of these phraseological units (in English "collar", in Uzbek "hand"), the general figurative meaning here is "the state of a person in which his body temperature rises". From here the general component "hot" ("hot") is taken;

10. lose countenance

identical components: lose = lose; non-identical components: countenance "self-control", power over oneself; The components "power over oneself" have the meaning "self-control", therefore, despite the difference in nominal components, these phraseological units have the same image;

11. flip one's lid (or wig) (lit. per. "fold the lid") - the roof went

identical components: lid= roof; non-identical components: flip ("fold"), let's go. The component "roof" in both languages means "head";

12. be on the rampage (literal translation "to be furious") - to be on edge identical components: be = to be; non-identical components: on the rampage "in a rage", on a platoon;

13. fly (or get) into a tantrum

identical components: tantrum = hysteria; non-identical components: fly into ("fall"), roll up;

14. drive (or send) smb. up the wall (lit. per. "drive someone on the wall") - climb the wall identical components: the wall = on the wall; non-identical components: drive up ("drive on"), smb. ("someone"), climb;

CONCLUSION: We see that in this group of phraseological units, incomplete equivalence is manifested either because of the difference in the verbal components of the compared languages, or because of the difference in nominal components. However, it is worth noting that the divergence of the component composition does not affect the general figurative meaning of the phraseological unit and its functional features.

When analyzing phraseological units with the meaning "Madness", we found that a significant part of the stable units in terms of their structure is non-equivalent (that is, phraseological units do not have any matches in vocabulary). However, at the same time, they note the identity of semantics (semantic equivalents). It should be emphasized that in the framework of this work, semantic equivalents mean only stable units of the studied lexico-semantic field, i.e. containing components with the meaning "madness".

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